

FUTURE MICROBOND TESTING – FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATION OF OPTICAL FIBERS FOR STRAINS

R. Dsouza¹, J. Jokinen¹, E. Sarlin¹, P. Antunes², and M. Kanerva¹

¹Tampere University, Faculty of Engineering and Natural Sciences, Tampere, FINLAND

²Physics Department & I3N and Instituto de Telecomunicações, Aveiro, PORTUGAL

Keywords: FBG, Microbond, Finite element modelling, Cohesive zone modelling

ABSTRACT

Adhesion is a significant property of fibrous composites since it affects the laminate level performance via micro-mechanics of the layers. The Microbond (MB) test is the most widely adopted micromechanical test to characterize the adhesion for single fiber-matrix interface. This test involves pulling the fiber out of a droplet against blades, resulting in damage at the fiber matrix interface. The test results show experimental data scattering, which calls for improvement on the MB test. In the current research, an attempt has been made to enhance the MB test by incorporating Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors for strain monitoring. This paper presents the Finite Element (FE) modeling and simulation of the MB test with FBG sensors for local strain sensing and improved understanding of the fiber droplet interface. The application of FBG sensors in fibers as a modification to MB testing is well demonstrated with a high-fidelity 3D FE model. Here, elastic-plastic behavior of the epoxy droplet is taken into consideration and Cohesive Zone Model (CZM) is employed to simulate crack onset and propagation. The study reveals the new data available by strain output in the test system provides more understanding of the interfacial behaviour.

1 INTRODUCTION

The estimation of the magnitude of adhesion between a fibre and matrix has been studied over the past three decades with various micromechanical tests, revolutionizing composites with the plethora of applications and techniques. There has been a broad innovative work for composite materials by combining different fibres and particles with various matrices that can be tailored to achieve desired properties. Fibres, matrix and the interface are the main factors influencing the mechanical performance of composite materials. The Microbond(MB) test developed by Miller [1] is the most widely adopted micromechanical tests to characterize fiber matrix interfaces. This test involves the pulling of the fiber out of a bead of matrix by knife edges resulting in the debonding of the fiber from matrix. The test applies small amount of material to produce test specimens but sample preparation is cumbersome in forming droplets of consistent diameter. Load and displacement are measured when a droplet is sheared off from the fiber. The MB test procedure has been used by various researchers to study different fiber-matrix systems that include glass fiber polycarbonate, glass fiber polypropylene and glass fiber epoxy [2].

Alongside experimental investigations, numerous Finite Element (FE) models have been developed over the past decades to study the underlying properties of the MB test. One of the challenges of FE modelling is to create a realistic droplet shape. The previously established Carroll theory [3] is used by several researchers to describe the droplet shape to be used in FE modelling. This also has paved the way in studying the different droplet sizes. An axisymmetric model was developed by Ash et. al.,

to study the MB test with different droplet shapes resulting in variation of stress (distribution) near the blade-droplet contact zone [4]. Taking the advantage of commercial softwares, different droplet shapes, such as cylindrical and spherical, including the effect of the meniscus, were also studied [5]. A study on stress distribution at the interface was investigated and results show the complexity of stress being shearing-peeling at the interface [6]. A study on 2D and 3D axisymmetric models of carbon fiber epoxy system has revealed that the stress distribution at the interface is greatly affected by blade geometry and blade separation [7]. Though the failure wasn't modelled, the results gave some insight of the blade separation effects.

With the advent of Cohesive Zone Modelling (CZM), numerous FE models have been developed using CZM to define the behaviour of the fiber matrix interface. Bilinear traction separation laws have been incorporated to study the crack propagation. The FE model for a microdroplet test using CZM for S-glass fiber epoxy matrix samples was developed highlighting the importance of residual stress and frictional sliding when fitting the traction separation laws [8]. Stress states at the interface for various non-linearities uplifts the importance of using CZM approach for crack onset and propagation. In addition to CZM, Coulomb friction law was incorporated into bilinear traction-separation law to define pure frictional sliding [9]. An FE model with a cohesive surface contact for carbon fibre epoxy has been studied recently to understand the variability in the measured interfacial shear strength and the likelihood of fibre breakage [10].

It is worth noting that all the aforementioned FE models rely only on one reliable test output that is force data. Most FE models use the measured peak force and fit the models accordingly. Damage onset and propagation is controlled using stress based, energy based or combined stress-energy criteria. There is a need for more advanced and comprehensive test methodology to accurately define the progressive interfacial debonding and unstable crack propagation. One such approach involves measuring strain during the MB experiment in an elegant manner providing strain-force curves as a benchmark for FE models. In this paper, Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) optical fiber is embedded with epoxy droplet and 3D FE models are studied to understand the influence of local strain in the MB test. Experimental results using this technique is used as a benchmark for FE simulations. Further force strain plots, effect of fiber strain at the interface and the effect of damage parameters on simulated fiber strain are discussed. Effect of blade separation distance and its importance for FE modelling are considered. Collectively, this paper presents and validates a novel technique of enhancing the existing MB setup for strain measurements using FE simulations.

2 FBG FIBER INCORPORATION

The traditional MB test, which is used to study fiber matrix systems, results only in a force displacement curve. Of this data, displacement is typically traced via test system control signal. Naturally, the validation of multi-parameter FE models becomes challenging. Measuring strain during the experimental process will not only enhance the MB test output but this modification will also help to discover new experimental results of adhesion. The modification also helps to measure residual strain during the droplet sample's curing process. An attempt to measure the strain during a MB process was demonstrated in 1997, by using Raman spectroscopy, for a carbon fiber epoxy (Araldite LY5052) system [11]. From stress-induced Raman band shifts, variation of strain along the embedded fibre regime was estimated. Though the system provides a good approximation of the fibre strain distribution it could be used only with clear transparent resins. Moreover the system becomes bulky and its calibration forms a challenging task considering a large series of MB tests to be performed. Taking into account the different aspects of MB tests, such as microdroplet size (in microns), the single fiber configuration (in microns), small force (approximately 0.01N to 2N) and, most importantly, the sensitivity of the experimental procedure,

Figure 1: Current strain measurement setup for microbond tests

FBG fibers are an excellent choice for strain measurement during a MB test. FBG fibres are small and lightweight making the best suitable option for measuring strains in a MB test. Typical FBG fibers consist of a small inner core, outer part (cladding) and an outer coating (shown in Figure 1). As FBG fibers stretch due to axial loading, the grating period and the refractive index changes with strain. Due to elasto-optic effect a change in the refractive index of the optical fiber caused by the variation in the length of the fiber core in response to the mechanical stress. The Bragg wavelength is given by the first order Bragg condition: $\lambda_b = 2 \times n_{eff} \times \Lambda$, where λ_b is the Bragg wavelength, n_{eff} the fiber core refractive index and Λ the period of the grating.

For the experiment, droplet (Epoxy resin- Araldite® LY5052, Hardener- Aradur® 5052) is laid on into the FBG optical fibre and bonded to the sample holder as shown in Figure 1. The fiber is connected to an FBG interrogator for strain measurements during a test. Force and strain values are recorded simultaneously. To prove the functionality of the modification and to further understand MB testing, FE modelling and simulation are carried out.

3 FINITE ELEMENT FORMULATION AND SIMULATION SCHEME

A 3D FE model is built taking into account all the critical experimental parameters. Previously, different studies on 2D axi-symmetric FE models have been carried out for different fiber droplet combination as discussed in Section 1. The approximation of droplets as 2D models hinders the understanding of the stress distribution around the interface. Hence, it is needed to define the entire experimental setup in 3D FE modelling. A recent study on aramid fiber epoxy resin, has incorporated a three dimensional FE model for MB test, showing the possibility of detailed interfacial study [12]. In this study, modelling and simulation of the MB setup is carried out using Abaqus® 2017, Standard (Dassault Systèmes).

The key highlights of the MB FE model are as follows,

- The entire model is three-dimensional, including droplet, fiber, blades, adhesive and the sample holder.
- The fiber is assumed to behave in a linear-elastic manner, droplet in an elastic-plastic manner with kinematic hardening conditions, adhesive and the sample holder in a linear-elastic manner. Blades are treated as rigid body elements with displacement as input during simulation.

- The fiber free length on the either side of the droplet and respective boundary conditions are considered in simulations.
- The fiber matrix adhesion is modelled using CZM.

The shape of the droplet is determined based on the images taken by optical microscope before the MB test. Image processing is carried out to identify the surface profile of the droplet using ImageJ® open source software. The extracted data points are then imported to Abaqus, giving the true shape of the droplet in three dimensions. This true shape of the droplet model allows to understand the stress and strain distributions across the embedded length of the fiber droplet. The sample holder is constrained in all DOFs while the ends of the fiber are constrained to sample holder with adhesives enabling the fixed constraint in all directions. The presence of sample holder in the FE model makes the simulation more realistic considering the boundary conditions in the global perspective. Input displacement is applied to the blades in the direction of the droplet. A section of elements are chosen on the loading side of the fiber having their characteristic length as that of the FBG sensor, where the strain output is recorded during the simulation. The material properties including the element type used in FE model is shown in Table 1.

Figure 2: Finite element model of the MB test comprising of a 3D droplet generation from optical microscope image, and examples of deformed and undeformed droplet shapes during simulation.

3.1 Interface Model

The interfacial behavior between the fiber and the droplet governs the quality of the bond. A strong fiber matrix bond makes composites more ductile and a weak bond leads to fracture of composites. Several models have been demonstrated to study the fiber matrix interfacial properties. Among all the models, CZM have been recently used due to its capability of modelling the fracture zone ahead of the crack tip. The CZM implemented in FE codes can precisely capture interfacial debonding causing separation between a fiber and matrix. It also has the capability of capturing the frictional sliding after debonding but shall not be discussed in this paper due to its complexity.

In the MB debonding process, the droplet debonds from the fiber with opening and shearing fracture mode, resulting in mixed mode delamination. To study this, a mixed mode traction separation law is needed. The undamaged linear elastic traction-separation behavior is defined as the product of cohesive

Table 1: Mechanical properties of the material constituents

Constituent	Young's Modulus (E) (GPa)	Poisson's ratio (ν)	Element type (code)	Diameter (mm)	Thermal expansion (α) ($10^{-6}/K$)
FBG Fibre	70	0.22	8-node linear brick (C3D8)	0.130	5
Epoxy *	3.2	0.35	8-node linear brick (C3D8R)	0.7318	97
Blades	220	0.29	8-node linear brick (C3D8)	-	-
Sample holder	3.2	0.37	4-node linear tetrahedron (C3D4)	-	-
Adhesive	1.6	0.29	4-node linear tetrahedron (C3D4)	-	-

* Yield stress of epoxy matrix is 60MPa.

stiffness (K) and contact separation (δ). The subscripts s , t , and n are the first and second orthogonal in-plane shear and the out-of-plane normal component of the traction vector at the cohesive contact element coordinate system, respectively.

$$\tau = \begin{Bmatrix} \tau_s \\ \tau_t \\ \tau_n \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} K_s & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & K_t & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & K_n \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta_s \\ \delta_t \\ \delta_n \end{Bmatrix} = K\delta \quad (1)$$

Here the cohesive zone is assumed to have a linear behaviour with a cohesive stiffness being constant ($K = 10^{13}Nm^{-3}$) in all three directions. A bilinear traction separation law is used in the current model as [13]:

$$\sigma = \begin{cases} K\delta & \text{if } \delta \leq a_0 \\ \frac{a_1 - \delta}{a_1 - a_0} \sigma_0 & \text{if } a_0 \leq \delta \leq a_1 \\ 0 & \text{if } \delta \geq a_1 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where,

$a_0 = \sigma_0/K$ and $a_1 = 2G_c/\sigma_0$. Here, σ_0 defines the damage onset, K defines the initial stiffness and G_c is the energy of debonding.

The current model utilizes a maximum stress criterion (Equation 3) for the damage onset and a mixed-mode power law criterion (Equation 4) for the damage evolution. The traction law for mode I component is assumed to be the same as shear mode II and mode III.

$$\max \left\{ \frac{\tau_s}{\tau_{s_{cr}}}, \frac{\tau_t}{\tau_{t_{cr}}}, \frac{\tau_n}{\tau_{n_{cr}}} \right\} = 1 \quad (3)$$

$$\left(\frac{G_I}{G_{I_{cr}}} \right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{II_{cr}}} \right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{G_{III}}{G_{III_{cr}}} \right)^\alpha = 1 \quad (4)$$

The inner surface of the epoxy droplet is used as slave surface and the outer surface of the fiber is used as master surface. The selection is ought to be based on the mesh density and consideration of the material properties of the fiber and the matrix. A hard frictionless contact is provided between the blades and the droplet.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Preliminary results

The separate force-displacement curve and strain-displacement curve obtained from simulations is shown in Figure 3. Both graphs have a very clear identifiable kink strain and kink regime. The position of the kink strain and force largely depends on the position of the blade which shall be discussed in Section 4.4.

The characteristic curve of strain almost resembles the characteristic curve of the force-displacement

Figure 3: Results of FE simulation (a) Force-displacement curve (b) Strain-displacement curve

Figure 4: Plot of force strain curve

curve in the global perspective for the currently used fibre matrix system. It is noted from the graphs that the relationship of strain-displacement and force-displacement is not linear up to the kink and then continues in almost a linear fashion. The non linearity of the force and strain profiles before the kink is due to the combined influence of droplet plasticity and the shape of the droplet. This indicates that the interface failure is not completely brittle as typically observed. In addition, the force-strain curve is plotted in Figure 4. The crack onset occurs at $\epsilon = 0.0026$ m/m followed by sudden debonding. A

small hysteresis is observed between the loading and the unloading curve that is expected as the droplet is modelled to behave in an elastic-plastic manner.

4.2 Embedded fiber strain

The study of fiber strains in various dimensions are presented in Figure 5. The distribution of strain in the embedded coordinate of the fiber is plotted at different blade positions. The fiber strain has a maxima at the fibre entry location and drops gradually to zero at the fibre exit. This characteristic curve behaves upto the damage onset. Once the damage onset has been reached, the maxima of the fibre strain slightly shifts away from the fiber entry. A 3D plot (Figure 6) reveals more information about the fiber strain. Projecting the maximum strain data points onto the strain-displacement plane shows that the

Figure 5: Variation of fiber strain with position along the droplet.

Figure 6: 3D plot of variation of fiber strain with position along the droplet as a function of blade displacement.

curve naturally forms the strain-displacement curve as shown in Figure 3 (a), which was extracted from the section of FBG fiber.

4.3 The effect of CZM parameters

The study on damage variables is been studied to evaluate the reported fiber strain at various conditions. The initial values of debond energy were estimated from a shear lag model [14] as presented in Equation 5,

$$G_c = \frac{rC_{33s}}{2} \left[\frac{F_d}{\pi r^2} + \frac{D_{3s}\Delta T}{C_{33s}} \right]^2 \quad (5)$$

where C_{33s} and D_{3s} are shear lag constants given by relationships,

$$C_{33s} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{1}{E_f} + \frac{V_1}{V_2 E_m} \right] \quad (6)$$

$$D_{3s} = \frac{1}{2} (\alpha_f - \alpha_m) \quad (7)$$

In Equations 6 and 7, α_f and α_m represents the thermal expansion co-efficient, E_f and E_m as Young's modulus, V_1 and V_2 as volume fraction of the fiber and the matrix respectively. The maximum traction (vector length) was chosen based fitting. Figure 7 presents the outcome of different values of debond energy (G_c) and maximum nominal traction (τ). Equation 5 results in $G_c = 50 \text{ J/m}^2$ and τ is obtained as 16 N/m^2 based on curve fitting. Further different values of G and τ are tested to verify the dependence of

Figure 7: The variation of fiber strain for different values of G_c and τ

the G_c and τ values for damage onset and evolution. As G_c value decreases and τ increases the damage tends to be more onset controlled. At lower debond energies, the shape of the droplet influences the displacement-strain curve significantly. Beyond $G_c = 130 \text{ J/m}^2$ the interface tends to be more growth controlled. It can be seen that the τ value remains constant after $G_c = 130 \text{ J/m}^2$, the reason being the entire interfacial damage is controlled by G_c and τ has very little contribution for the strain-displacement curves shape.

A more intensive study on the stress distribution across the interface at various positions is reported in this paper. Figure 8 shows the distributions of stress (normal and tangential) and Von Mises stress at 4 different locations around the interface. Four paths were chosen to study the stress distribution along the fiber axial coordinate. Path 1 and Path 2 are run at the blades where the surface contact between the rigid blades and the droplet. Path 3 and Path 4 are the locations where the blades do not physically get

Figure 8: Plots of stress distribution along fiber axial coordinate

in contact with the droplet. The data is plotted just before the damage onset point (load level). Path 1 and Path 2 exhibit the dominance of shear stress. Path 3 and Path 4 exhibit the dominance of stress in the normal direction (peeling). The magnitude of Von mises stress is considerably high for path 1 and path 2 as the maximum deformation of droplet is seen at these regions.

4.4 The effect of blade positioning

The influence of blade separation distance on the stress distribution along the interface has been studied in the current literature. The effect of blade position have been studied earlier by changing the blade separation distances and plotting the variation of Interfacial Shear Stress (IFSS) [15]. It was observed that the normalized IFSS value increased with increase of the distance between the fibre and the blade.

In this study the the behaviour of strain for various blade positions is analysed. The distribution of stress along the fiber axial coordinate is also studied to understand the change of behaviour of strain during the debonding process. Figure 9 shows different positions (point of contact) used for simulations.

Figure 9: Different blade positions used for FE simulations.

(a) Stress distribution along fiber axial coordinate for different blade positions.

(b) Fiber strain-displacement plot for different blade positions.

Figure 10: Influence of blade position on Shear stress and strain.

Three different blade positions are used: from $25 \mu\text{m}$ to $185 \mu\text{m}$ as shown in Figure 9. The respective stress distributions and strain-displacement graphs are plotted in Figure 10a and Figure 10b. The stress distribution along the interface is greatly affected by an increase in blade position. Increase in blade position increases by small amount of force and strain maxima. It is worth noting that, as the blade position moves towards the droplet side, the observed kink varies significantly both in the case of force and strain. As the blade separation increases a large surface area of the deforming droplet gets in contact with the blades decreasing the damage onset. As the blade separation increases, damage onset strain decreases strain(kink).

Figure 11: Microbond test setup for single fiber test with FBG incorporation

Figure 12: Microbond test setup for single fiber test with with strain gauge incorporation

5 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper investigates the potential implementation of strain sensors in MB testing. To overcome the lack of required output data from MB testing, a novel technique of incorporating FBG optical fibers is proposed to measure strain during the debonding process. This approach accounts for more enhanced MB setup providing two reliable output parameters namely force and strain.

FE analysis is carried out to validate the proposed concept followed by a detailed sensitivity analysis. Study reveals a good validation for the proposed idea providing more insights in fiber embedded strains, effect of blade positioning and damage parameters. This work can be further extended for MB tests on varieties of fibre matrix combinations. One such modified setup is presented in Figure 11. Here, the single fiber in test is coupled with FBG fiber using a deformable coupler, which is bonded to the sample holder for MB tests. The lightweight and simple structure of FBG fibers allows one to keep the fiber intact and carry out the measurements. A modification using strain gauges is also presented in Figure 12. Geometrical corrections would be required for the sample holder to make the system more elegant with strain gauges. A study on shrinkage effect and curing cycle assesment during sample preparation shall be carried out for a future study.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 764713. Authors want to acknowledge M. Kakkonen for assistance with experimental activities and CSC – IT Center for Science (Finland) for computational resources.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Miller, P. Muri, L. Rebenfeld, A microbond method for determination of the shear strength of a fiber/resin interface, *Composites Science and Technology* 28 (1) (1987) 17–32.
- [2] X. Gao, R. Jensen, S. McKnight, J. Gillespie Jr, Effect of colloidal silica on the strength and energy absorption of glass fiber/epoxy interphases, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 42 (11) (2011) 1738–1747.
- [3] B. Carroll, The accurate measurement of contact angle, phase contact areas, drop volume, and laplace excess pressure in drop-on-fiber systems, *Journal of colloid and interface science* 57 (3) (1976) 488–495.
- [4] J. Ash, W. Cross, D. Svalstad, J. Kellar, L. Kjerengtroen, Finite element evaluation of the microbond test: meniscus effect, interphase region, and vise angle, *Composites Science and Technology* 63 (5) (2003) 641–651.
- [5] S.-K. Kang, D.-B. Lee, N.-S. Choi, Fiber/epoxy interfacial shear strength measured by the microdroplet test, *Composites Science and Technology* 69 (2) (2009) 245–251.
- [6] T. Schüller, U. Bahr, W. Beckert, B. Lauke, Fracture mechanics analysis of the microbond test, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 29 (9-10) (1998) 1083–1089.
- [7] G. Pandey, C. H. Kareliya, R. P. Singh, A study of the effect of experimental test parameters on data scatter in microbond testing, *Journal of composite materials* 46 (3) (2012) 275–284.
- [8] S. Sockalingam, M. Dey, J. W. Gillespie Jr, M. Keefe, Finite element analysis of the microdroplet test method using cohesive zone model of the fiber/matrix interface, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 56 (2014) 239–247.
- [9] G. Nian, Q. Li, Q. Xu, S. Qu, A cohesive zone model incorporating a coulomb friction law for fiber-reinforced composites, *Composites Science and Technology* 157 (2018) 195–201.
- [10] Q. Zhao, C. Qian, L. Harper, N. Warrior, Finite element study of the microdroplet test for interfacial shear strength: Effects of geometric parameters for a carbon fibre/epoxy system, *Journal of Composite Materials* 52 (16) (2018) 2163–2177.
- [11] X. Gu, R. Young, Deformation micromechanics in model carbon fiber reinforced composites part II: The microbond test, *Textile research journal* 67 (2) (1997) 93–100.
- [12] M. Kanerva, S. Korhikoski, K. Lahtonen, J. Jokinen, E. Sarlin, S. Palola, A. Iyer, P. Laurikainen, X. Liu, M. Raappana, et al., DLC-treated aramid-fibre composites: Tailoring nanoscale-coating for macroscale performance, *Composites Science and Technology* 171 (2019) 62–69.
- [13] G. Alfano, On the influence of the shape of the interface law on the application of cohesive-zone models, *Composites Science and Technology* 66 (6) (2006) 723–730.
- [14] R. Scheer, J. Nairn, A comparison of several fracture mechanics methods for measuring interfacial toughness with microbond tests, *The Journal of Adhesion* 53 (1-2) (1995) 45–68.
- [15] C. Zhi, H. Long, M. Miao, Influence of microbond test parameters on interfacial shear strength of fiber reinforced polymer-matrix composites, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 100 (2017) 55–63.